

CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES ORIGIN AND METHODS OF TREATMENT

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Abstract. *Diseases of the cardiovascular system - diseases of the heart, arteries and veins. They are many and varied. Some of these diseases (rheumatism, myocarditis, etc.) damage the heart, some arteries (atherosclerosis) or veins (for example, thrombophlebitis), others damage the entire cardiovascular system (hypertension).*

Keywords: *heart, aorta, stenosis, heart diseases, diagnosis and treatment.*

Diseases of the cardiovascular system remain the main cause of disability and death worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, 56% of all deaths are caused by diseases of the cardiovascular system. In European countries, cardiovascular diseases cause the death of 4.3 million (48%) people per year.

According to the State Statistics Committee, 62.1 percent of citizens who died in the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-June 2019 were caused by diseases of the circulatory system.

Diseases of the cardiovascular system are closely related to a person's lifestyle and existing risk factors. While most risk factors can be controlled by lifestyle changes, some (hypertension, dyslipidemia, and diabetes) can be corrected with medication.

Professor Lee Sang-chul from the multidisciplinary Seoul Samsung Medical Center clinic in South Korea recently visited Tashkent for patients with cardiovascular diseases and those who want to undergo preventive measures against these diseases. participated in the event.

In the program, the professor gave information about types of heart diseases, dangerous conditions and signs in the blood system, as well as advice on preventing the listed problems.

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Notable professor Lee also gave his advice on heart diseases and modern treatment methods at the Himedi consultation center in Tashkent. Let's get acquainted with some of them:

Cardiomyopathy is a disease associated with primary damage to the myocardium - it is the presence of structural and functional negative changes in the heart muscle in the absence of cardiovascular diseases, arterial hypertension, acquired and congenital heart defects.

The real reasons for the occurrence and development of cardiomyopathy have not yet been determined. There are a number of factors that trigger the occurrence of this disease: heredity, negative effects of the external environment, viral infections, autoimmune diseases, endocrinological diseases, exposure to allergens, alcoholism, heart pathologies, etc.

In the initial stage, cardiomyopathy is usually asymptomatic. The patient may have the following complaints: pain in the heart area, severe fatigue, general weakness, severe heaviness in the right rib cage, shortness of breath, shortness of breath and other similar symptoms.

Treatment of cardiomyopathy depends on its type:

- hypertrophic cardiomyopathy is a thickening of the heart muscles and, as a result, a violation of the heart's blood pumping function. Medicines are prescribed by doctors, but septal myectomy surgery is recommended in cases of danger. As a result of the operation, the thickened heart muscles are reduced and normal blood circulation is restored.

- dilated cardiomyopathy is a state of expansion of the main blood-pumping chamber of the heart - the left ventricle, in which the heart is unable to fully pump blood.

- in restrictive cardiomyopathy, the heart muscles harden and their elasticity decreases. As a result, the heart does not expand and the heart does not fill with enough blood per heartbeat.

An electronic cardiac pacemaker that generates impulses for a slow beating heart, a defibrillator for a dangerously unstable heart, an auxiliary ventricular implant for a heart with impaired blood pumping, is offered to the patient as a solution to improve the condition of the patient in various situations, especially when drugs cannot help. advice can be given - the doctor emphasized.

A defect in the wall between the heart valves is a persistent defect, deficiency and changes in the anatomical structure of the heart that interfere with normal blood flow. It is one of the most common congenital heart defects in children older than 3 years. In this condition, there is a hole(s) in the interdispheric septum (wall) that separates the right and left atria in the heart. The presence of this hole causes pathological blood flow from the left atrium to the right and can cause heart and lung problems in the future.

The main method of researching the disease is echocardiography, which provides detailed information about the defect, the condition of the heart, etc.

The modern method of treating the disease is the endovascular method. In this case, a long tube-shaped catheter is inserted into the heart through the femoral vein and the defect is closed using a special coating.

If the size of the defect is large, minimally invasive surgery may be recommended. In this case, the operation can be performed through a 4-6 cm incision in the right part of the patient's chest.

Coronary artery bypass grafting – This procedure is used to restore blood flow to blocked or severely narrowed coronary arteries. The essence of the method is that the surgeon creates a "shunt" (spare blood vessel) bypassing the blocked coronary arteries to restore blood flow.

A blood vessel transplanted from the patient's leg is used as a shunt. As a result of this type of surgery, the proper blood flow is restored in the patient.

Transcatheter aortic valve replacement (TAVR) is usually recommended for patients diagnosed with severe aortic stenosis. When blood is pumped from the heart to the body, the aortic valve opens, and when it does not open and close properly, the patient is diagnosed with aortic stenosis. As a treatment for this disease, it is recommended to replace the worn and narrowed aortic valve, which causes moderate blood flow in the body. Transcatheter aortic valve replacement is sometimes called transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI).

TAVR is a minimally invasive surgical procedure in which a tube-shaped catheter is guided into the heart through a large blood vessel in the leg or through a small incision in the chest, and an implant is placed to replace a worn-out aortic valve. After the implant, the old aortic valve is removed. The new implant starts working immediately.

The decision to treat aortic stenosis with TAVR is made for each individual after consultation with a multidisciplinary team of cardiac medical and surgical specialists.

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